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ABSTRACT BOOK

**HEALTH MANAGEMENT:
MANAGING THE PRESENT
AND SHAPING THE FUTURE**

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Management of pharmaceutical waste: the practices and perception (example from Serbia)

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Context

The current literature data suggest that improper disposal of medicines is a global problem and that the most common reason reported for not returning medicines to pharmacies or other collection sites is lack of information and awareness on the existence of available collection schemes in the community. This research aimed to examine the current methods of disposal of unused medicines from households in Serbia, willingness of Serbian residents to participate and bear the costs of organising the unused medicines collection program and to define factors contributing to an individual's willingness to participate and pay for a medicine collection program.

Methods

The survey included randomly selected patients older than 18 years visiting private pharmacies in the four largest Serbian cities. Data were collected by trained interviewers during the period from December 2017 to November 2018. The questionnaire included information regarding the presence of unwanted medicines within the household, general medicine disposal practices, the likelihood to participate in a medicine take back program, willingness to pay for a medicine disposal program (per prescription and per visit), importance to the environment, and demographic variables from participants. The data was analysed by basic descriptive statistics, nonparametric statistical tests and advanced econometric modelling.

Results

The most commonly reported reasons for the presence of unused medicines within households were not finishing the full therapy (34%) and not knowing what to do with the expired medicines (19.8%). Although most of the respondents believed the most appropriate disposal method for unused medicines was returning them to a pharmacy (81.9%), the most reported disposal method was throwing medicines into the garbage (59.1%). The majority of respondents had never received advice about the proper disposal of medicines from households nor participated in an organised collection program. 80% of respondents are very or somewhat likely to participate, however less than half of the respondents are willing to pay for the collection of their unused medicines. The factors that influenced willingness to participate are environmental awareness and income, while the factors affecting willingness to pay, are previously received advice about proper disposal, education level, number of unwanted medicines in the household and gender.

Discussion

Targeted public educational campaigns should be organised continuously, but advice on proper medicine disposal must routinely follow medicine dispensing. Educating the general public about environmental concerns is an essential step in altering disposal practices, however to result in more pro-environmental behaviour it is necessary to make the action easy and use the familiar locations such as pharmacies as collection locations. The model where pharmacies take financial responsibility for the disposal of unused medicines without some kind of reimbursement is not recommended. One of the valuable solutions is an implementation of the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) laws which require that pharmaceutical manufacturers manage their products in all phases of their life cycle, including end of life treatment and waste management. To comply with this legislation pharmaceutical manufacturers and others involved in the product chain should plan, manage and fund take-back programs to ensure the collected medicines are properly managed.